

ADHESION BETWEEN A FLAX FIBER AND BIOBASED THERMOSET MATRIX

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1 General introduction

Amongst the thermoset resins, epoxy and polyester resins are the most commonly used for composites which require high mechanical performances. The main drawbacks for the using of thermoset resins are their uneasy recyclability and the toxicity of their constituents and solvents. During the epoxy resin common synthesis, an epoxy precursor reacts with an amino or acid anhydride hardener. The traditional epoxy precursor in the industry is the Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) (Fig. 1), obtained from Bisphenol A (BPA), a toxic component for human and environment, and epichlorohydrine.

Fig. 1. DGEBA chemical formula.

Epichlorohydrine and BPA come traditionally from petroleum resources. In order to reduce the environmental impact of the thermoset resins made with petroleum reserves, alternative renewable resources are available. The renewable substitutes may be either the epoxy precursors, or the (amino or anhydride) hardeners. Epichlorohydrine can be produced from biosourced glycerol. Solvay set in place in 2007 the EPICEROLTM process [1] which uses this technology. Dow Epoxy, Spolchemie and Sicomin with its Greenpoxy 55[®] use biobased epichlorohydrine for epoxy resin production as well. By using biobased epichlorohydrine, renewable carbon content is still poor because epichlorohydrine represents a minor part in the final resin structure. Biobased BPA brings much higher renewable carbon content. The EpobioxTM resin of the Amroy society, is made with biobased BPA and its renewable carbon content stands between 50 and

90%. Like epichlorohydrine, biobased BPA is still harmful (CMR 2 product). Epoxydised oils can be good candidates as epoxy precursors, which would avoid the use of DGEBA. Since 1996, natural triglyceride oils have been used as a basis for polymers, adhesives, and composite materials [2][3]. These oils can be derived from plant or animal sources, and are made up mainly with triglyceride molecules, whose structure is presented in Fig. 2. Triglycerides are composed of three fatty acids joined at a glycerol juncture. Most common oils contain fatty acids that vary from 14 to 22 carbons in length, with 0 to 3 double bonds per fatty acid [4]. The epoxydised triglyceride oil can react with an amino or anhydride hardener to produce an epoxy matrix resin.

Fig. 2. Triglyceride molecule [4].

Now, most of the major resins producer has a “green” range of resins. The bio-content is not always measured according to the same method, though. The american standard ASTM D 6866-12 [5] allows to determine the renewable carbon content. It is based on the carbon dating method. Another way to quantify the renewable content is to give a weight percentage of the biocontent in the final resin. Generally speaking, in order to guaranty the optimal performances for composites, a good adhesion between fiber and matrix is required. The adhesion between polymers and vegetal fibers has often been criticized and numerous treatments have been tested in the literature to improve the fiber/matrix interface [6][7]. The aim of this article is to measure the adhesion between flax fibers and partially biobased epoxy resins available on the market, and to

compare the results to these obtained for the petrochemical commonly used equivalent. The adhesion between the resins and a flax fiber will be investigated at the microscopic scale via the debonding test. As the quality of adhesion between fiber and matrix has an influence on the in-plane shear resistance, in plane shear test will be carried out on ± 45 laminates composites at the macroscopic scale. The results of adhesion at the both scales will be linked together.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Flax fibers

Two different batches of fibers have been considered. The flax fibers used for the debonding test belong to the Melina variety (harvested in 2009) and were supplied by La Calira company (Picardie, France). They were dew retted to help fibre extraction then scutched and hackled. No further treatment was applied to the fibers. The second batch is used for making the composites samples for the in-plane shear test. It consists in flax fibers in the form of layers of two unidirectional tapes of untwisted yarns in a 0/90 configuration, stitched together with cotton thread, supplied by C.R.S.T (France) with a weight of 500 g/m². The fibres were grown in France and had been dew retted before stripping and combing.

2.2 Epoxy matrix

The study focuses on commercialised epoxy matrix. Given that each main resin producer has its green range of matrix, only matrices with a renewable

carbon content superior to 50% have been retained as “partially biobased matrix”. A petrochemical reference has also been selected. The studied matrix and their characteristics (biocontent, origin of biocontent and curing specifications) are gathered in the Tab. 1.

2.3 Matrix tensile test

Tensile test on the matrix have been carried out on the apparatus MTS Synergie RT1000 (MTS, Eden Prairie, MN, USA). The laboratory atmosphere is controlled at a temperature of 23°C and a humidity of 48%. Tensile testing followed ISO 527 instructions. The loading speed was 2 mm/min. Extensometer HTE was used with a nominal length of 49.7 mm. The tests were carried out at least five times for each specimen and the results were averaged arithmetically.

2.4 Samples preparation for in-plane shear test

Specimens for in-plane shear were prepared according to ASTM D3518 [8] with the different matrices reinforced by (± 45) flax layers. Volumic fiber content is around 24%. The shear test standard requires a $[45/-45]_{ns}$ stacking sequence with $2 < n < 4$, and at least 8 reinforcement layers to limit tension-flexion coupling [9] and increase the interlaminar area. Laminates were made with 8 reinforcement layers under thermo-compression and rectangular coupons were milled with the following dimensions: (25 x 180 x 3) mm³.

Matrix	Biocontent		Origin of biocontent	Curing specifications
	ASTM D6866	Weigth percentage		
Petro	Petrochemical		-	2h at 120°C
Biobased A	55±2	-	Biobased epichlorhydrine	24h at Tamb + 24h at 40°C
Biobased B	-	50-55	Biobased BPA, pine oil	2h at 80°C

Tab. 1. Studied epoxy matrix.

2.5 Density and fibers fraction in composites

Density of matrices and composites is measured with MS-DNY-54 Toledo Mettler scales. By weighing the sample in air and in ethanol, the density can be deduced by the calculation (1).

$$\rho_{sample} = \frac{M_{air} \rho_{air} - \rho_{ethanol}}{M_{air} - M_{ethanol}} + \rho_{ethanol} \quad (1)$$

Volumic fibers content is deduced from density according to the equation (2).

$$V_f = \frac{\rho_{composite} - \rho_{matrix}}{\rho_{fiber} - \rho_{matrix}} \quad (2)$$

An observation of the sections showed no significant porosities.

2.6 Debonding test

The droplets were placed on the flax fibres using a single glass fibre which had been dipped in the epoxy resin. Fibers with droplets are placed in an oven to cure according to the specifications of each resin supplier (see 2.2). Microbond specimens were then checked under the microscope to control the droplet geometry. Samples with defects (kink bands on the fibre or lack of symmetry of the droplet) were systematically rejected. Besides being symmetrical, microdroplets need to be smaller than 150 µm length otherwise the fibre will break when loaded. Droplet length and height, and fiber diameter at both extremities are measured for the selected samples. Then the flax fibre with the epoxy microdroplet was mounted in the shearing device and continuously observed with a microscope. The fiber was pulled out of the droplet while the latter was constrained by the knife edges (Fig. 3). The loading rate during debonding was 0.1 mm/min.

Fig. 3. Debonding test [10].

Force–displacement plots were recorded for each specimen, in order to determine the debonding force and the friction force. At least 20 specimens were tested for each matrix. The interfacial shearing rupture mode is checked by an observation of the debonded droplet.

2.7 In-plane shear test

In-plane shear test has been carried out according to ASTM D 3518[8] on an Instron tensile testing machine equipped with a 50 kN capacity load cell, and loaded at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 2 mm/min up to rupture. The laboratory atmosphere is controlled at a temperature of 23°C and a humidity of 48%. A biaxial extensometer measured the sample width and thickness variation during the test. At least five samples have been tested for each matrix.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile mechanical performances of the matrix

Results of the tensile test are presented in the Fig. 4 and values of Young’s modulus, strength at break and strain at break are reported in the Tab. 2.

Fig. 4. Tensile performances of the matrix

The best performances in terms of Young modulus and tensile strength are attributed to the petrochemical matrix. The Biobased A resin shows properties close to these ones of the petrochemical matrix. This result is not surprising because these both matrix are based on the same components,